

SELF-DEVELOPMENT IN INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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Abstract: The article discusses the identification of students' personal potential in inclusive education, the formation of their abilities for independent thinking, self-awareness and self-development, the individual characteristics of students studying in an inclusive environment, psychological and pedagogical support tools and the main tasks facing teachers, the fact that education in an inclusive environment involves not only achieving academic results, but also the formation of the student as a person, social adaptation, emotional stability, the fact that in the educational process, students need to support such processes as determining their own potential, setting personal goals, independent thinking, critical analysis and finding their place in life, the formation and stimulation of students' ability to self-development, the fact that students studying in inclusive education have different cognitive, physical and social needs, the need for an approach aimed at their personal growth is even more acute, inclusive education should include all children and students, including those with disabilities, is an educational system that provides for training in general education institutions, and this approach is aimed at ensuring social justice, equality and individual development, creating a comfortable and adapted educational environment for students, organizing psychological and pedagogical support, taking into account the individual needs and abilities of students in the educational process, and expanding their opportunities for self-development.

Key words: inclusive, inclusion, integration, education, student, desire, aspiration, mastery, ability, thinking, performance, competence, analysis, task, result.

Introduction. One of the main trends in education at the modern stage of human development is the creation of equal opportunities for people of all backgrounds and abilities. From this point of view, an inclusive education system serves to create conditions for individual development not only for people with disabilities, but also for all students. In an inclusive environment, students not only master academic knowledge, but also have the opportunity to identify their potential and determine the path of personal development. The 21st century is the era of a knowledge society based on human capital, in which the personal capabilities, abilities and social activity of each person are becoming an important factor in the development of society. The principles of inclusive education are being widely introduced within the framework of global changes in the education system, sustainable development goals and policies aimed at ensuring social equality [14]. Inclusive education is a system of providing equal, high-quality, and adapted education for all students with different abilities. Its main task is to expand students' opportunities for self-awareness, self-management and self-development.

This article analyzes the factors influencing the self-development of students in the process of inclusive education, pedagogical approaches, psychological foundations, and advanced strategies used in practice. Also, in this process, the role of the teacher and educational environment, the importance of factors such as reflection, motivation, and social support are highlighted on a scientific basis.

Main part. Education in an inclusive environment involves not only achieving academic results, but also the formation of the student as a person, social adaptation, and emotional stability. This requires supporting such processes as identifying students' own potential, setting personal goals, independent thinking, critical analysis, and finding their place in life during the educational

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process. To achieve these goals, it is very important to form and encourage students' ability to develop themselves.

Especially since students studying in inclusive education have different cognitive, physical, and social needs, the need for an approach focused on their personal growth becomes even more acute. After all, each student is a unique individual who is worthy and capable of development. The education system should be a mechanism that reveals these opportunities [7, 8].

Inclusive education is an educational system that provides for the education of all children and students, including those with disabilities, in general education institutions. This approach is aimed at ensuring social justice, equality and individual development. The main tasks of this system are the following [11, 12]:

- Creating a comfortable and adapted educational environment for all students;
- Organizing psychological and pedagogical support;
- Taking into account the individual needs and abilities of students in the educational process;
- Expanding opportunities for self-development.

Self-development (Russian: саморазвитие, English: self-development) is a complex, dynamic process aimed at a person's conscious self-improvement, deepening his knowledge and skills, and revealing his inner potential [13]. This process is based on the following scientific foundations:

- humanistic psychology (K. Rogers [11], A. Maslow [5]): a person is a creative being who, with self-awareness, strives for self-improvement;
- theory of activity (L.S. Vygotsky [1]): development takes place through activity;
- motivational theories (D. McClelland [4]): internal motivation motivates a person to develop himself.

Students studying in an inclusive environment have different cognitive, emotional and physical capabilities [2]. In this case, the approach to personal development must be individual. The following factors influence students' self-development:

- humane and respectful treatment;
- interactive teaching methods that ensure active participation;
- coordinated reflection and counseling processes;
- social support groups and mentoring systems.

In order to ensure self-development of students in inclusive education, the pedagogue should use the following opportunities:

- a road map suitable for each student's abilities and opportunities;
- understanding, evaluation and control of one's own knowledge;
- monitoring the student's personal achievements and development dynamics;
- encouraging the student to make independent research and decisions.

In world practice, platforms and approaches that ensure personal development are effectively used in many inclusive educational institutions. For example:

- In the Finnish education system, special psychological support centers operate to identify and develop students' own potential;
- In Japan, students analyze their actions and feelings every day through a "self-development diary";
- In Uzbekistan, inclusive education centers have also been established in some higher education institutions, where students are provided with individual route-based advice [9].

Results and Discussions. Inclusive education enables all students, including those with disabilities, to receive education in mainstream education institutions. This approach serves the purpose of social justice, equality and equal opportunities for all. The inclusive environment itself ensures development based on individual and collective needs.

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Self-development as a dynamic, conscious personal movement is associated with activity theories and humanistic psychological perspectives (Maslow, Rogers). Thus, Vygotsky's activity theory emphasizes that personal development occurs through the activity being performed. Motivation and internal demands play a key role in this process [3, 4, 1].

- Academic Self Concept (ASC) is a student's perception of their academic ability, success and potential. Some studies have found that SEN students in inclusive settings have lower levels of ASC [6].

In inclusive education settings, teachers develop students' emotional and social skills by effectively constructing the internal environment. A study conducted in Spain shows that inclusive pedagogy significantly improves students' social and emotional competencies sciencedirect.com. In addition, SEL (social-emotional learning) programs have been linked to improved empathy, stress resistance, and academic performance in children [3].

When it comes to self-development and intrinsic motivation, students tend to have lower levels of intrinsic motivation than extrinsic motivation. This hinders their academic performance and development. Developing intrinsic motivation ensures students' resilience and increases their chances of success, and improves students' academic performance by creating differentiated teaching methods and teaching that meets their individual needs.

Metacognitive activities (reflection, portfolio) enable students to monitor, analyze, and set goals for their academic and personal development.

Approaches implemented in countries and universities that support inclusive education include, for example, Finland, Japan, and Australia, which have centers aimed at supporting the emotional and motivational state of students, or have introduced educational resources in an online environment.

Inclusive education is an approach that includes all students, including those with disabilities, those with learning difficulties, and those from diverse social and cultural backgrounds, and involves joint learning. In such an environment, the individual needs, abilities, and potential of each student should be taken into account, and conditions should be created for their personal growth and full participation in society.

In the inclusive education system, the ability of students to develop themselves is very important, because:

1. Increases independence, learns to control their own learning process, which prepares them for an independent life in the future.
2. Facilitates social integration, students who work on themselves and believe in their own abilities participate more actively in society. This is especially important for students with disabilities.
3. Forms motivation and confidence, a student who sees his own personal achievements increases interest and motivation to study.
4. A student who actively participates in the learning process, aims for self-development, is active in the lesson, asks questions, seeks and actively interacts.

The following factors are important for the self-development of students in the process of inclusive education:

- individual educational programs - adapted to the specific characteristics of each student;
- psychological and pedagogical support - stimulating motivation and instilling confidence;
- cooperation with peers - mutual assistance and the formation of social skills;
- interactive and digital technologies - facilitate independent learning;
- self-assessment and reflection skills — students understand their achievements and problems, determine their next steps.

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Conclusion. Self-development of students in the conditions of inclusive education not only realizes personal potential, but also motivates them to take a worthy place in society, become socially active and develop as equal citizens. Therefore, it is necessary for educational institutions to create an environment conducive not only to academic knowledge, but also to personal growth.

In inclusive education, students' self-development is critical to their academic and personal success. The following are important for the effective organization of this process:

1. Formation of an educational environment that supports personal development in inclusive educational institutions;
2. Organization of special retraining courses for teachers;
3. Use of technologies that provide motivation and reflection in the educational process;
4. Implementation of the system of assessment and monitoring of individual potential of students.

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